

KNOWLEDGE AND PERCEPTION ON CONSEQUENCES OF ABORTION AMONG
ADOLESCENTS IN AMASSOMA COMMUNITY, BAYELSA STATE

¹Onasoga, Olayinka A., ²Kayode, Olubunmi Titilayo, ¹Owei Anita

¹Faculty of Nursing, Department of Maternal and Child Health Nursing, Niger Delta University,
Wilberforce Island, Bayelsa State, Nigeria

²FCT School of Nursing, Gwagwalada, Hospital Abuja, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Unsafe abortion has been described as a schoolgirl's problem in Nigeria, where 80% of patients admitted to hospitals with abortion-related complications are adolescent girls. Hence, this research study was conducted to assess knowledge and perception on consequences of abortion among adolescents in Amassoma Community, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. A simple size of 120 respondents was drawn from the target population using purposive sampling technique. Data were collected using questionnaire and the information obtained was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics and level of significant was set at 5%. The study revealed that majority of the respondents 61% were between the ages of 17-21 years with a minimum age of 12years and maximum age of 25 years; with a mean age of 18 and standard deviation of 2.28. The study revealed that majority of the respondents 89% had adequate knowledge of the consequences of abortion and believed that abortion is a sin and is done by immoral girls, yet more than half 60% of the respondents will encourage a person to do abortion and will even consider abortion in case of unwanted pregnancy. Majority of the respondent opined that abortion can be done in case of rape; mental illness and when the mother's life is in danger but 40% of the respondents said they will never go for an abortion under any circumstances. The study also revealed that there was a significant association between the age of respondents and the level of knowledge; as well as significant association between the level of knowledge and perception on the consequences of abortion with $p < 0.05$. It is recommended that Public enlightenment programmes on unsafe abortion and its consequences should be given to adolescents for value clarification and proper attitude transformations

KEYWORDS: Abortion, Adolescents, Consequences, knowledge, Perception.

WORD COUNT: 286

Received for Publication: 20/12/12

Accepted for Publication: 14/02/13

Corresponding Author: yinka_onasoga@yahoo.com.

INTRODUCTION

Complications from spontaneous abortions and unsafely induced abortions pose a serious global threat to women's health and lives (International Women's Health Coalition, 2008). An estimated 46 million induced abortions are performed annually; about 20 million are unsafe, and 98% of these take place in the developing world where most humanitarian emergencies take place. (World Health Organization, 2007a)

Unsafe abortion accounts for an estimated 13% of pregnancy related deaths representing approximately 70,000 maternal deaths and more cases of maternal morbidity every year (WHO, 2003; WHO, 2007b). In developing countries, access to family planning is often limited, and misconceptions and myths about effective contraceptives inhibit female adolescents from using them, causing many to have unplanned and unwanted pregnancies. It is estimated that across the developing world, 36% of pregnancies are unintended (Alan Guttmacher Institute, 1998). One-quarter of world's women live in countries where abortion is highly restricted or banned outright and approximately 19 million unsafe abortions and 75,000 abortion-related maternal deaths occur each year worldwide (WHO, 1998).

Journals© 2013. All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournals.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

According to Alan Guttmacher Institute (2008), 83% of all abortions are obtained in developing countries and 17% occur in developed countries, 64.4% of all abortions are performed on never-married women; Married women account for 18.4% of all abortions and divorced women obtain 9.4%, 1% of all abortions occur because of rape or incest; 6% of abortions occur because of potential health problems regarding either the mother or child, and 93% of all abortions occur for social reasons (i.e. the child is unwanted or inconvenient). In the U.S, 52% of women obtaining abortions are younger than 25; women aged 20-24 obtain 32% of all abortions; Teenagers obtain 20% and girls under 15 account for 1.2%.

Nigerian law makes it a crime to perform or to obtain an abortion except to save a woman's life. Penalties exist for any person who performs an abortion, as well as for any woman who seeks an abortion or who attempts to cause her own miscarriage. Nevertheless, women in Nigeria obtain abortions, many from physicians providing the service in private clinics and hospitals. Still, unsafe methods of abortion continue to be used widely, resulting in severe health consequences for women (Okonofua *et al.*, 1996). Unsafe abortion has been described as a schoolgirl's problem in Nigeria, where 80% of patients admitted to hospitals with unsafe abortion-related complications are adolescent girls. Hence it becomes necessary to assess the level of knowledge and perception on consequences of abortion among adolescents in Amassoma Community, Bayelsa State.

Objectives of the study

1. To assess the level of knowledge on the consequences of abortion among adolescents in Amassoma Community, Bayelsa State
2. To determine the perception of abortion among adolescents in Amassoma Community

Hypothesis

- There is no significant relationship between age of adolescents under study and their level of knowledge on consequences of abortion.
- There is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge on consequences of abortion among adolescents and their perception towards abortion.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

A descriptive research design was used for this research and the study was carried out in 2012 in Amassoma community, which is an Ijaw speaking community in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The community is made up of 22 compounds with Niger Delta University at the centre of the community. It is bounded by Ogobiri community on the North, Oporoma on the South, on the East is Otuan while on the West is Torubeni. Amassoma Community is a developing community with a population of 155,000. Out of this number, 84,234 are males while 70,766 are females. Aside the indigenes, Amassoma is a home to people of different ethnic groups e.g. Yoruba, Hausa, Igbo, Urhobo and Isoko, with the College of Health Sciences at one end of the community while a general hospital situated right inside the College of Health Sciences. The target population consists of all adolescents in Amassoma Community, Bayelsa State and a purposive sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 120 adolescents from the target population using the "Rule of Thumb" which says that 25% of the study population can be used. Data was collected using a self-developed questionnaire after an extensive literature review on abortion. The questionnaire consists of 25 item questions of qualitative and quantitative variables of 3 sections namely: socio-demographic data, knowledge on consequences of abortion, perception on abortion.

Permission was sought for and obtained from the leader of the community. Thereafter, respondents were briefed about the purpose of the study and their right to participate, or withdraw from the study. The respondents were informed on the benefits and reasons for the research study. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents was ensured, as all records obtained were used purely for the purpose of the research.

Both descriptive and inferential statistics will be used to analyze the data collected. Descriptive statistics in the form of frequencies, percentage, bar charts, pie and a score below five was awarded low knowledge and a score

of five and above was awarded high knowledge; while Pearson’s Chi square (X^2) was used to establish statistical relationships between the variables

RESULTS

Out of the 120 questionnaires administered to respondents only 100 were retrieved and same was analyzed and represented on tables and figures which are shown below and testing of hypotheses generated.

Table1: Showing Frequency Distribution of Demographic Data (n= 100)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
AGE	23.0	23.0
12-16 years	61.0	61.0
17-21 years	16.0	16.0
22-25 years		
Religion		
Christianity	91	91.0
Islam	8	8.0
Traditional	1	1.0
Tribe		
Ijaw	42	42.0
Hausa	7	7.0
Igbo	22	22.0
Others	29	29.0
Marital status		
Single	91	91.0
Married	9	9.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1 shows that majority of the respondents 61(61%) were between the ages of 17-21 years, while 23(23%) were between ages 12-16 years and only 16 (16%) were between 22- 25years. Majority 91(91%) were Christian, among the ethnic group, majority 42(42%) were Ijaw while 7(7%) were the Hausas, majority 91(91%) were single while 9(9%) were married.

Table 2 Showing Mean Age of Respondent (n= 100)

Variable	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mode
Age	13	12	25	18.19	2.28	19

Table 2 shows that the minimum age of the respondents was 12years and the maximum age was 25, with a mean age of 18.19 and standard deviation of 2.28.

Figure 1 shows that all the respondents (100%) have heard of the consequences of abortion

Figure2: Showing Sources of Information about Abortion (n= 100)

Figure2 shows that majority 42(42%) of respondents, got information about abortion from school, 20(20%) from religion institution, 18 (18%) from mass media, 12(12%) from friends, 7 (7%) from conference and only 1 (1%) from parents

Table 3: Showing knowledge of Respondent about consequences of abortion (n=100)

Variables Response		Frequency	Percentage
Abortion can lead to severe bleeding	Yes	97	97.0
	No	3	3.0
Abortion can damage the womb	Yes	76	76.0
	No	24	42.0
HIV/AIDS can be contracted from abortion	Yes	82	82.0
	No	18	18.0
Abortion can cause infertility	Yes	71	71.0
	No	29	29.0
Abortion can prone one to infection	Yes	83	83.0
	No	17	17.0
Abortion can lead to death	Yes	83	83.0
	No	17	17.0
TOTAL		100	100.0

Table 3 shows that majority of the respondents97% said abortion can lead to severe bleeding while 3% said no. Most of the respondents 76 opined that abortion can damage the womb (uterus) while 24 said otherwise. Majority of the respondents 71% said abortion can cause infertility while 29% said it cannot.83% of the respondents said that abortion can prone one to infection while 17% disagreed.83% of the respondents opined that abortion can lead to death while 17% opined it cannot.

Figure 3: Showing level of knowledge of Respondent about abortion (n=100)

Figure 3 shows that majority of the respondents 89% have high level of knowledge on consequences of abortion while 11% have low level of knowledge about it

Table4: Showing Perception of Respondents on Abortion (n=100)

RESPONSE TO PERCEPTION QUESTIONS ON ABORTION		Frequency	Percentage
Abortion is a sin	Strongly agree	40	40.0
	Agree	30	30.0
	Disagree	12	12.0
	Strongly disagree	18	23.0
Abortion is done by immoral girls	Strongly agree	55	55.0
	Agree	10	10.0
	Disagree	21	21.0
	Strongly disagree	14	17.0
I will advise or encourage a person to go for an abortion	Strongly agree	10	10.0
	Agree	26	26.0
	Disagree	22	22.0
	Strongly disagree	42	42.0
I will going for an abortion in case of unwanted pregnancy	Strongly agree	48	48.0
	Agree	12	12.0
	Disagree	15	15.0
	Strongly disagree	25	25.0
Abortion can be done in case of rape	Strongly agree	40	51.0
	Agree	24	30.0

	Disagree	10	12.0
	Strongly disagree	4	5.0
Abortion can be done Case of mental illness	Strongly agree	28	28.0
	Agree	25	25.0
	Disagree	22	22.0
	Strongly disagree	25	25.0
Abortion can be done if the mother's life is in danger	Strongly agree	34	43.0
	Agree	36	46.0
	Disagree	8	10.0
	Strongly disagree	22	22.0
I will never go for an abortion under any circumstances	Strongly agree	23	23.0
	Agree	17	17.0
	Disagree	40	40.0
	Strongly disagree	20	20.0

Table 4 shows that Majority of the respondent 70% agreed said abortion is a sin while 30% disagreed. 65% of the respondent said abortion is done by immoral girls while 35% said no. 64% said that they will advise or encourage a person to do abortion while 36% said otherwise. 60% will consider abortion in case of unwanted pregnancy while 40% will not. In case of rape 64% said person should do abortion while 36% said no. Majority of the respondent 53% opined that abortion can be done in case of mental illness while 47% said no. 70% of the respondent said that abortion can be done if the mother's life is in danger while 30% said no. 40% of the respondents said they will never go for an abortion under any circumstances while 60% said they will do it.

Table 5: showing associations between the level of perception, demographic variables and level of knowledge towards abortion. (n=100)

Variables	Level of knowledge			Pearson Chi-Square X^2 p-value Df	Remark
	Low knowledge	High knowledge	Total		
Age	12 – 16	7	16	$X^2 = 25.76$ P-Value=0.001 df=2	Significant association
	17 – 21	9	52		
	22 – 25	2	14		
	Total	11	89		
Perception	Positive	3	73	$X^2 = 14.879$ P-Value=0.000 df=1	Significant association
	Negative	8	16		
	Total	11	89		

Table 5 shows that there was a significant association between the age of respondents and the level of knowledge; as well as significant association between the level of knowledge and perception with $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Majority of the respondents 61(61%) were between the ages of 17-21 years with a minimum age of 12 years and maximum age of 25, with a mean age of 18.19 and standard deviation of 2.28. This indicates that majority of the respondents are in their prime age. Majority of respondents were Christians and were single. This indicates that Christians and singles predominates the study area. Majority were Ijaws.

Journals© 2013. All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

Majority of the respondents said that abortion can result in severe bleeding, infection, damage to the womb, infertility and can lead to death. This implies that Majority of the respondents have adequate knowledge on the consequence of abortion. Most of the respondents got their information from school, friends, and mass media respectively. According to International Women's Health Coalition, (2008), Complications from spontaneous abortions and unsafely induced abortions pose a serious global threat to women's health and lives. In many other cases, unsafe abortion causes countless long-term consequences such as chronic pain, pelvic inflammatory disease, tubal occlusion and secondary infertility. Unsafe abortion accounts for an estimated 13% of pregnancy related deaths representing approximately 70,000 maternal deaths and more cases of maternal morbidity every year (WHO, 2003; WHO, 2007b).

Finding revealed that Majority of the respondents' aid that abortion is a sin and abortion is against their belief but less than a quarter opined that abortion is done by immoral girls. The role of religious beliefs is a major consideration, as most religious beliefs oppose abortion and this is one of the factors that influence the respondent's attitude towards abortion.

Half of the respondents said that they will consider abortion in case of unwanted pregnancy. Most of the respondent said that they will advise or encourage a person to do abortion if there is genuine reason need for it. Majority of the respondent said that a person should be allowed to do abortion in case of incest, rape, mental illness ,mother's life in danger and all the respondent opined that abortion should done in the case of foetal abnormality. This corroborates the finding of Craig, Kane, and Martinez (2002). That for reasons of "women's health", "rape", and "birth defect", abortion rights received widespread support. Hewson (2001) contended that denying a woman the right to an abortion is unethical, because it serves to subordinate women to a reproductive end. She asserted that the prospect of woman's forced suffering as the result of pregnancy is a moral issue in and of itself. Additionally, Hewson argued that a foetus' right should not interfere with a mother's right to autonomy. Also, Furedi (2001) contended that women do not have abortions for abstract reasons or reasons of principle; they have them because pregnancy is intolerable. Both Furedi and Hewson assert that pregnancy subjects a woman to a condition that is not bearable. 40 % of the respondent said that they will never go for an abortion under any circumstances. Abortion has been controversial, as it involves legal, ethical, religious, and political aspects. From a legal perspective a woman may be able to seek an abortion depending upon the circumstances; however, the legality of abortion does not indicate the woman has a moral right to have an abortion. Some of the ethical issues involved with the moral right of abortion include the question of when life begins and the controversy of woman's rights versus the rights of the foetus (Craig et al., 2002).The study revealed that there was a significant association between the age of respondents and the level of knowledge; as well as significant association between the level of knowledge and perception on consequences of abortion with $p < 0.05$.

CONCLUSION

The study assessed the level of knowledge and perception on consequences of abortion among adolescents in Amassoma Community, Bayelsa State. The study revealed that majority of the respondents had adequate knowledge of the consequences of abortion and believed that abortion is a sin and is done by immoral girls, yet more than half of them will encourage a person to do abortion and will even consider abortion in case of unwanted pregnancy. Majority of the respondent opined that abortion can be done in case of rape; mental illness and when the mother's life is in danger but 40% of the respondents said they will never go for an abortion under any circumstances. The study also revealed that there was a significant association between the age of respondents and the level of knowledge; as well as significant association between the level of knowledge and perception on the consequences of abortion with $p < 0.05$.

Implication of the study to the Nursing Profession

Professional Nursing\Midwives have a key role to play in broadening the knowledge of the public on consequences of unsafe abortion in order to reduce its complication. Hence, the following recommendations were made:

Journals© 2013. All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](#) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](#)

- Public enlightenment programmes on unsafe abortion and its consequence should be given to adolescents for value clarification and proper perception transformations
- Government should endeavor to educate and enlighten the general populace on need to support safe abortion services by giving good social support thus reducing stigmatization associated with abortion.

REFERENCES

Alan Guttmacher Institute (2008). Induced abortion worldwide, Facts in Brief, New York: AGI.

Craig, S. C., Kane, J. G., and Martinez, M. D. (2002). Sometimes You Feel Like a Nut, Sometimes You Don't: Citizens' Ambivalence about Abortion. *Political Psychology*, 23/2: 285–301

Furedi Ann (2001). Issues for service providers: a response to points raised *J Med Ethics*;27:suppl 2 ii28-ii32doi:10.1136/jme.27.suppl_2.ii28

Hewson Barbara (2001). Reproductive autonomy and the ethics of abortion *J Med Ethics*;27:ii10-ii14 doi:10.1136/jme.27.suppl_2.ii10

International Women's Health Coalition (2008). Safe Abortion - International Women's Health Coalitioninfo@iwhc.org

Okonofua, Friday E., Clifford Odimegu, Bisi Aina, P.H. Darn, and A. Johnson (1996). *Women Experiences of Unwanted Pregnancy and Induced Abortion in Nigeria*, Summary Report, New York: Population Council.

World Health Organization (1998). Unsafe Abortion: Global and Regional Estimates of Incidence of and Mortality Due to Unsafe Abortion with a Listing of Available Country Data, third ed., Geneva:WHO,

World Health Organization (2003). Safe Abortion: *Technical and Policy Guidance for Health Systems*, Geneva: WHO

World Health Organization (2007a). "Unsafe abortion: Global and regional estimates of the incidence of unsafe abortion and associated mortality in 2003. Fifth edition." (Geneva) <http://www.who.int/reproductivehealth/publications/unsafeabortion>

World Health Organization, (2007b). Facts on unsafe abortion.
